

A NEW DEVICE DESIGNED TO ENHANCE HAZELNUT OIL EXTRACTION

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Abstract

The hazelnuts represent important widely consumed tree nuts from the mountain areas in many countries, appreciated for their nutritional composition and valuable oil quality given by unsaturated fatty acids, especially oleic (80%) and linoleic (6%–12%) acids. Due to its bioactive substances, hazelnut oil is used in different fields of industry, such as food, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics. Various methods were applied to hazelnut oil extraction, but finding alternative eco-friendly methods to obtain a high oil yield and high-quality extracted oil become a current issue. One of these methods consists of mechanical pressing assisted by ultrasound. A new device designed for oil extraction from oilseeds which includes a transducer with ultrasound and a concentrator that ensures uniform pressures throughout the mass undergoing extraction can be applied to improve hazelnut oil extraction yield. To carry out the extraction, the hazelnuts are heated beforehand to a temperature of approximately 70 °C, the extraction mechanical pressure is in the range of 25-30 MPa, and the amplitude of the acoustic signal from the ultrasound generator transducer, 60 – 100 μm. During the extraction, the pressing zone ensures a temperature of 70 – 90 °C. Constructive elements and proposed extraction parameters ensure the optimization of the ultrasound-assisted extraction process. The performance features of this device make its use feasible for oil extraction from hazelnuts and allow for increasing the extraction yield of oil, being suitable for industrial production.

Keywords: hazelnut; hazelnut oil; oil extraction methods; mechanical pressing; ultrasounds.

INTRODUCTION

The hazelnut (*Corylus avellana*, Betulaceae) is an important economic forest tree in Mediterranean countries, Turkey being the main producer in the world accounts for about 63.5% of world production (UNSD 2023) and is followed by Italy, the United States of America, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Chile (UNSD 2023; Bacchetta et al. 2015). In European Union countries, the total hazelnut production in 2021 was 118 080 t, while in Romania it was 660 t, showing the popularity of hazelnuts around the world (UNSD 2023). China, as one of the original countries of native *Corylus* species, had 8 species and 2 varieties. Approximately 15 varieties of hybrid hazelnuts were selected at the end of the twentieth century and were released gradually from the year 2000 to 2010 (Jiang et al. 2021).

The tree generally grows in temperate climate zones with relatively high humidity and a high rainfall rate, is 3–8 m high, lives 75–100 years, and produces 8–10 kg of nuts per year. Each nut is covered by a husk and a shell, and ripens around October, when the husks dry and release the kernels to fall on the ground (Celenk et al. 2020).

Hazelnuts can be consumed roasted or raw, chopped, or whole, and are widely used in many areas from confectionery to ice cream, bakery products to chocolate (Alasalvar et al. 2010), various processed food products containing hazelnuts, such as spreadable chocolate, cereals, cookies, nougat, pastry, ice cream, and cooking oil, hazelnut oil often integrated into food products (Moscetti et al. 2012; Yaman et al. 2023).

The hazelnut kernels play a considerable role in human nutrition and health due to their specific composition of lipids (52- 69%), most of which are monounsaturated fatty acids, mainly oleic acid, protein (12-28%), carbohydrate (12-22%), dietary fiber (8.70%), minerals salts (2.00-3.05%), vitamins (especial vitamin E), phytosterols (mainly β -sitosterol), squalene and phenolic compounds (Celenk et al. 2020; Jiang et al. 2021; Schlörmann et al. 2015; Stănică et al. 2023). Research on the mineral elements reported that K, P, Ca, and Mg are the elements that predominate in hazelnuts, while Mn, Zn, Fe, Cu, B, Ni, Pb, and Cd elements are minor (Çetin et al. 2020; Müller et al. 2020; Stănică et al. 2023), playing an essential role in human metabolism. Studies on the different hazelnuts grown in the United States reported that characterization results regarding proximate composition, lipid oxidation status, and mineral content were in ranges like those reported for hazelnuts from Asian and European growing regions, each cultivar possessing a unique nutritional profile (Zhao et al. 2023). The variations in nutrient composition were dependent of growth conditions and climate that change from year to year (Müller et al. 2020). The beneficial effects of phenolic compounds on human health related to their antiallergenic, antiatherogenic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antithrombotic properties were reported in many studies (Karaosmanoglu Ustun 2021; Salas-Salvadò Megias 2004).

Studies on different hazelnut species revealed that the hazelnut kernels nutritional composition is different among species, with wild hazelnut kernels having higher bioactivity substance content (vitamin C, total tocopherol, total phenol, and total flavonoid) and antioxidant capacity (Jiang et al. 2021). On the other hand, the hybrid hazelnut had a higher content of oil, oleic acid, α -tocopherol, and sugar compared with wild hazelnut. The amino acid profiles of some Chinese hazelnut species were similar to the composition of the Turkish hazelnut (Jiang et al. 2021; Köksal et al. 2006).

A considerable amount of research has been performed on the nutritional values and physicochemical features of hazelnut oil, revealing that is appreciated as a valuable edible oil for health food. The high quality of hazelnut oils is related to the composition of fatty acids. Oleic acid is the most abundant fatty acid in hazelnuts, accounting for 70–80% of the fatty acid composition, followed by linoleic, palmitic, and stearic acid (Balta et al. 2006; Król et al. 2019; Yaman et al. 2023). In a study on hazelnut kernels collected from Germany and Turkey, was reported that the oil yields range from 8.1 to 64.1%, the main fatty acids in hazelnut kernel oils being oleic (76.3–82.6%), linoleic (6.5–14.0%), and palmitic (5.7–6.5%) (Matthäus Özcan 2012). In the same study, was shown that an appreciable amount of α -tocopherol (19.9–63.9 mg/100 g), with a mean value of 40.02 mg/kg, and γ -tocopherol (1.3–15.5 mg/100 g), with a mean value of 4.84, α -tocopherol is the predominant tocopherol found in hazelnut kernel oils (Matthäus Özcan, 2012). Another study showed that hazelnut oil consists of more than 90% unsaturated fatty acids, especially oleic (80%) and linoleic (6%–12%) acids, being also a good source of vitamin E (α -tocopherol) that improves shelf life by its antioxidant capacity (Jokić et al. 2016). Due to its composition, unsaturated fatty acids, sterols, and tocopherols, hazelnut oil has essential roles in preventive medicine.

Currently, hazelnut oil is used mainly in salad dressings and cosmetic and pharmaceutical products (Jokić et al. 2016).

As a functional product due to its components which are expected to have additional health functions beyond basic nutritional properties, edible cold-pressed hazelnut oil is used for cooking, salad oil, and also for food preparation. Additionally, hazelnut oil has great potential in the pharmaceuticals and cosmetics industries due to its valuable bioactive substances such as tocopherols and tocotrienols, polyunsaturated fatty acids, free and esterified sterols, phenolics, lignans, squalene, triterpene alcohols, carotenoids, phospholipids, potassium, and magnesium (Boskou 2017; Moreau Kamal-Eldin 2015). Virgin hazelnut oil showed greater and longer moisturizing effects than refined hazelnut oil in a cosmetic emulsion, the phospholipid concentration of hazelnut oil is directly associated with a skin moisturizing effect (Masson et al. 1990).

The researchers described various extraction methods of oil from hazelnuts, each with its own advantages and challenges. The yield, quality, and characteristics of the oil can be considerably influenced by the extraction methods. A representation of the basic methods applied to obtain oil from hazelnuts can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Oil extraction methods

Chemical extraction involves organic solvents depending on the chemical characteristics of the raw material and produces low-quality oil that requires extensive purification operations.

Aqueous enzymatic extraction has the potential to minimize the loss of oil quality and can be used as an alternative to solvent extraction. The hazelnut oil extracted from raw hazelnuts by using 2% Pectinex®, 2% Viscozyme®, or their equal mixture (2% based on

hazelnut weight) provides an oil yield and the quality characteristics of extracted oil comparatively with oil obtained by solvent extraction (chloroform: methanol) (Ermış et al. 2018). The solvent extraction method of oil presents many disadvantages such as toxicity, high-cost solvents, and being harmful to the environment (Celenk et al. 2020).

By using supercritical fluid extraction method, the oil yield is lower than extraction with n-hexane, but no significant differences were noted between the two oils regarding the composition of acyl lipids and sterols (Celenk et al. 2020). Oils obtained by carbon dioxide extraction contain more tocopherols and are slightly more stable than oils extracted with n-hexane. However, the oxidative stability of carbon dioxide-extracted oils is lower than that of solvent-extracted oil despite the high content of tocopherols in carbon dioxide-extracted oils (Celenk et al. 2020; Moreau Kamal-Eldin 2015).

The mechanical oil extraction methods, such as hydraulic pressing and screw pressing, do not require the use of organic solvent and, moreover, the bioactive compounds such as essential fatty acids, phenolics, flavonoids, and tocopherols are retained in the oil (Al Juhaimi et al. 2018). Additionally, these methods offer the possibility of using cake free of toxic solvents in other processes. Valuable and substantial compounds such as tocopherols, squalene, and sterols were reported in cold-pressed hazelnut oil (Veysel U Celenk et al. 2018; Celenk et al. 2020). However, physical processes like screw pressing present as disadvantage the low oil extraction yield (Cakaloglu et al. 2018).

Therefore, finding alternative eco-friendly methods like mechanical techniques becomes the current issue in obtaining high-quality oil. Simple usage, rapid realization, short duration of the process, and high-quality oils are the main advantages of mechanical applications. On the other hand, low yield is the biggest disadvantage of mechanical techniques, but this technique can be optimized to reduce the yield by up to 4%–6% by preheating the seeds. Oil extraction applications have some basic and unalterable rules such as not damaging the oil during operation, least impurity, minimum oil content in the cake, and maximum oil yield (Celenk et al. 2020).

Various techniques have been investigated to extract the oil from hazelnuts since the previous research showed that hazelnut oil can control the adverse effects of hypertension and decrease the cholesterol level in the blood (Durak et al. 1999). In a previous study, hazelnut oils were extracted through microwave-assisted (Uquiche et al. 2008), and supercritical carbon dioxide extraction without the applied ultrasound. These are considered low-yield extraction methods because only 45.3% and 59.0% of oil recovery were achieved by using microwave-assisted extraction (Uquiche et al. 2008) and supercritical carbon dioxide extraction (Özkal et al. 2005) respectively. Another study showed that hazelnut oil was extracted by pressing (Jokić et al. 2016), but the problem faced was high energy consumption for pressing although it can achieve 77% of oil yield (Jokić et al. 2016). On the other hand, the disadvantage of screw-based oil extraction devices for oilseeds is that they do not apply the same pressure to all the raw materials being pressed. The lack of uniform pressure results in low extraction yields that can be increased by using supercritical fluids, such as CO₂, an environmentally friendly solvent (Jokić et al. 2016), but it is expensive.

Nowadays, ultrasound application is widely used in nut and seed oil extraction to enhance the oil yield (Chemat et al. 2017; Geow et al. 2018). The CN 203792751 U patent revealed an oil press capable of improving the quality of oil pressing which includes a horizontal pressing screw that works with an ultrasonic device. Filling and emptying the

extraction cavity for each extraction has the disadvantage of low productivity (US 005974959).

To the best of our knowledge, the application of ultrasound and a concentrator that ensures constant pressure throughout the raw material mass from which extraction is performed has not been explored in the edible oil extraction process. The current study aimed to present a new extraction oil device designed to enhance oil extraction yield from oilseeds or nuts. The device is using during oil extraction by mechanical pressing of oilseeds an ultrasonic transducer that increases the extraction efficiency and a concentrator that ensures constant pressure throughout the mass of raw material from which the extraction is carried out (RO 132758 B1). The novelty element resides in its feasibility to be used to improve hazelnut oil extraction yield.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

The ultrasound-assisted extraction device (Mironeasa et al. 2022) includes three distinct work posts: loading post (I) with the raw material to be extracted (Figure 3), mechanical pressing (P) (Figure 2) assisted with an ultrasound transducer, and evacuation post (E), Figure 4. The top view of this device is presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 2. Transversal section by pressing the post

Fig. 3. Transversal section by loading post

Fig. 4. Transversal section by evacuation post

The piece of a special form that has the role of a sieve in device construction is represented in Figure 6.

The loading post (I) has a magazine in contact with a base plate which allows a cylindrical cavity in an upper plate rotatably arranged on the base plate (Figure 3) to be filled with raw material such as hazelnuts. The pressing post (P) comprises an ultrasound generator transducer having at its lower part a concentrator arranged in a pressing cavity provided in the base plate (Figure 2), in the lower part of the pressing cavity a sieve formed

in a cylindrical body and a conical one being provided, the sieve being traversed by bores and having external channels executed which allow the oil to flow during pressing towards a tank. The evacuation post (E) comprises a punch that evacuates the by-product resulting from pressing the hazelnuts through a chute mounted on the base plate (Figure 4).

Fig. 5. Top view of the device

Fig. 6. Detail piece sieve type

The successive transition from one work post to another is achieved by rotating the upper plate using a stepper motor that performs 60° indexing of the upper plate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The constructive elements for each work post of dispositive and corresponding work principle described in RO 132758 B1 patent (Mironeasa et al. 2022) are presented in this paper section. Hazelnuts are found in the mountain forests or can be cultivated in these areas for human consumption. As oleaginous raw materials, hazelnuts can be processed to obtain hazelnut oil at a high extraction yield.

The loading post (Figure 3) has a magazine (26) in contact with the base plate (18) (Figure 2) which allows the cylindrical cavity in the upper plate (20) to be filled with the hazelnut to be pressed. The filling is carried out up to the upper edge of the upper plate (20), the lower wall of the magazine (26) (Figure 3) acting as a separator.

The pressing post comprises the pressing part formed by the ultrasound generator transducer (1) which has at its lower part, the concentrator (3) and the cavity (a), Figure 2. The constructive form of the concentrator (3) ensures constant pressure throughout the mass of hazelnuts subjected to pressing. A frustoconical ring (2) is mounted on the upper part of the concentrator rod to ensure the sealing of the cavity (a) when pressing begins. The extraction is carried out in the cavity in the form of a bore (a) made in the base plate (18). The base plate is provided with two cavities to ensure the pressing and evacuation of the briquette resulting from the oil extraction. In the lower part of the pressing cavity, at the pressing post, there is a piece acting as a sieve (6). Piece (6) is made up of two bodies: one

cylindrical and one conical, Figure 6. Piece (6) is traversed by bores and has external channels that allow the oil to flow during pressing towards the tank (5). The angle of the conical body of the piece (6) is smaller than the angle of the bore in the base plate (18) to allow better oil drainage.

At the base of the bore in the base plate (18), an orifice (c) is made which allows the oil to flow outwards from the base plate (18) into the reservoir (5) attached to the base plate. To seal the extraction area, gasket (2) is mounted on concentrator (3), and sealing ring (25) is mounted on upper plate (20). Any oil losses due to the sealing made with the ring (25) are taken over by the circular channel (b) made in the base plate (19) and provided with an opening that communicates with the opening (c). Under the cavity of the pressing station is the electrical resistance (7) which has the role of maintaining a constant temperature during the oil extraction.

The evacuation post (Figure 4) comprises a punch (23) which has a diameter close to the bore diameter (a), achieving a tight fit. The ejection of the briquette resulting from the pressing is possible by making two concentric bores in the base plate (18). The bore located in the upper part has a diameter close to the diameter of the bore (a) forming a clearance fit with it, and the second bore has a larger diameter to facilitate the evacuation of the briquette of pressed material. After exiting the bores, the briquette is directed outside the evacuation area by the chute (27) which is mounted on the base plate (18).

The successive transition from one work post to another is possible by rotating the upper plate (20) (Mironeasa et al. 2022). The rotational movement is ensured by the stepper motor (13) which performs three 60 ° indexing of the upper plate (20). In the case of designing a sequence of work posts, the indexing angle of the positions of the upper plate (20) can be changed by the stepper motor. The sequential rotation movement is taken from the motor (13) and transmitted via the pinion (15) to the gear wheel (8) which transmits the movement via the key (14) to the vertical shaft (24). The gear wheel (8) is fixed to the shaft (24) with the nut (9). The shaft (24) is mounted on the radial bearing (19) which is fixed to the base plate (18) via the elastic ring (16) and to the shaft (24) via the elastic ring (17). The upper plate (20) can rotate relative to the base plate (18) by taking the rotation movement from the shaft (24) via the key (22). The upper plate (20) can rotate relative to the base plate (18) due to the bearing on the axial bearing (21). Ensuring the concentricity of the two upper plates (20) and lower (18) is achieved through the edge (d) existing on the lower plate.

The base plate (18) rests on the welded assembly formed by three legs (10) mounted at equidistant distances and provided with soles (12). The welded assembly formed by the three legs (10) is stiffened by the circular plate (11) which has a cutout for the motor (13).

The extraction is carried out by ultrasonically assisted mechanical pressing. To achieve an optimal extraction, the hazelnut moisture must be between 17-18%. To carry out the extraction, the hazelnuts are heated beforehand to a temperature of approximately 70 °C. The extraction pressure is carried out mechanically, at values between 25 and 30 MPa. To increase the extraction yield of oil from hazelnuts, the ultrasonic transducer is activated during mechanical pressing. The amplitude used for extraction varied between 60 and 100 μm. During the extraction period, which is 35 - 40 s, a temperature between 70 and 90 °C is ensured in the pressing area.

This device for oil extraction presents the following advantages (Mironeasa et al. 2022):

- provides the pressure necessary to break the hazelnuts to extract the oil;
- it can be easily provided with an automatic working regime;
- constructions can be made with the three posts arranged in a circular sequence, posts that work in parallel;
 - by using the concentrator, uniform extraction pressures are ensured throughout the mass of raw material subjected to extraction;
 - the piece acting as a sieve ensures the passage of the oil to the collection tank and can be easily replaced or cleaned if it becomes clogged;
 - by executing the oil collection channel, after the sealing elements, a better collection of the oil is ensured in the event of a possible lack of tightness of the extraction area between the concentrator and the extraction cavity;
 - the method reduces the extraction time and intensifies the extraction, which determines a high yield;
 - the method according to mass transfer theories by applying ultrasound increases the permeability of cells under pressure and the diffusion of the secondary metabolite;
 - as a result of pressing, a compact pressed by-product is obtained that can be used for other purposes, such as fiber in food, fertilizer, fuel source, etc.

CONCLUSION

In this article, the new device presented, designed for oil extraction from oilseeds, can be applied for hazelnut oil extraction offering increased yield extraction. The constructive and functional parameters allowed the improved hazelnut oil extraction yield, decreasing the extraction time. The extraction method applied, mechanical pressing assisted by ultrasound is eco-friendly and the device can be manufactured at a low cost. The implementation of such a device for the valorization of hazelnuts from mountain area presents some benefits for the mountain economy sector. Moreover, the by-product that remains after the extraction of oil from hazelnuts is safe and has strong potential for the production of fortified foods, functional products, food ingredients, or pharmaceutical purposes due to its high nutritional value and valuable components. The research needs to be continued to evaluate the quality of hazelnut oil obtained by using this new device.

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AUTHOR(S) CONTRIBUTION

S.M. and C.M. contributed equally to this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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